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Non-Profit Organizations in the Italian Regions

Between 2015 and 2020 they grew by 10.22%

Istat calculates the number of non-profit organizations. Nonprofits are defined as the share of nonprofits per 10,000 population. The data refers to the period between 2015 and 2020 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the regions by value of non-profit organizations in the Italian regions in 2020. Valle d'Aosta is in first place for the value of non-profit organizations with a value of 115.00 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 114.80 units, and from Friuli Venezia Giulia with 91.20 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont with an amount of 70.40 units, followed by Molise with a value of 69.10 and Basilicata with an amount of 68.60 units. Puglia closes the ranking with a value of 48.90 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 47.00 units and Campania with a value of 39.60 units.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change of non-profit organizations in the Italian regions between 2015 and 2020. Calabria is in first place for the value of the percentage change of non-profit organizations between 2015 and 2020 with an amount of 24,55% equal to a variation from 44 units up to 54.8 units. Molise follows with a value equal to 20.8% corresponding to a variation from 57.2 units up to a value of 69.1 units equal to an amount of 11.9 units. In third place is Campania with a value equal to 19.64% equal to a variation from 33.1 units in 2015 up to 39.6 units in 2020. In the middle of the ranking we find Lombardy with an amount of 9.87 % corresponding to a variation from an amount of 52.7 units up to a value of 57.9 or equal to a variation of 5.2 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to an amount of 9.58% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 66.8 units up to a value of 73.2 units corresponding to a value of 9.58%. Below is Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 9.32% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 105 units up to a value of 115 units corresponding to a variation of 9.8 units. Veneto closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of 4.12% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 60.7 units up to a value of 63.2 units equal to an amount of 2.5 units. Marche follows with a variation equal to 2.96% corresponding to an amount of 74.2 up to a value of 76.4 or equal to 2.2 units. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of 2.64% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 60.5 units up to a value of 62.1 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Abruzzo, Emilia Romagna, Veneto, Lazio, Lombardy, Basilicata, Molise, Calabria, Piedmont, Sardinia, Puglia, Sicily, Liguria, Campania, Tuscany, Marche, Umbria.
- Cluster 2: Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto-Adige, Friuli Venezia Giulia.

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From the point of view of the clusters we can see the following ordering: $C2 > C1$. The regions in which there are the largest non-profit organizations are Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige and Friuli Venezia Giulia. The other regions, however, present medium-low levels of presence of non-profit organisations. However, since cluster 1 includes too large a number of non-profit organisations, it is possible to propose a further classification by setting $k=3$ and optimizing with the Silhouette coefficient. By setting $k=3$ it is possible to verify whether a subdivision of the regions occurs which can in some way reflect the size of the Italian macro-regions. We can thus identify a structure of three clusters composed as follows:

- Cluster 1: Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige, Friuli Venezia Giulia;
- Cluster 2: Puglia, Sicily, Calabria, Campania, Lombardy, Lazio;
- Cluster 3: Liguria, Piedmont, Sardinia, Tuscany, Marche, Basilicata, Molise, Veneto, Umbria, Abruzzo, Emilia Romagna.

In this case it is possible to verify the presence of the following cluster ordering: $C1 > C3 > C2$. The leading regions are always Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige and Friuli Venezia Giulia. However, in second place are the regions of cluster 3 which brings together very heterogeneous regions from both an economic and geographical point of view. Finally, the last cluster in terms of number of non-profit organizations is made up of cluster 2 essentially made up of 4 southern regions added to Lombardy and Lazio. Since the variable analyzed takes into consideration the number of non-profit organizations per 10,000 inhabitants, it is very likely that regions with small populations are more favored than populous regions. For example, Valle d'Aosta with around 130 thousand inhabitants is in the top cluster while Lombardy with around 10 million inhabitants is in the last cluster. This could also be the reason for the presence of Molise and Basilicata in the third cluster instead of the second, like the other southern regions. However, net of this distinction we can note that generally the southern regions tend to perform worse than the regions of the Center and North, with the exception of Lazio and Lombardy.

Conclusions. The number of non-profit organizations grew between 2015 and 2020, going from an amount of 63.77 units per 10,000 inhabitants up to a value of 70.29 units per 10,000 inhabitants, i.e. a variation of 10.22%. We can note that this growth occurred above all in the southern regions, i.e. in Southern Italy with a value of +18.29%, in the South with a value of +16.28%, in the Islands with an amount of 12.95%. The percentage growth was lower in the central-northern macro-regions which however had higher levels in absolute value than the southern macro-regions throughout the period considered. In fact, the absolute value of non-profit organizations in the South is 23.14% lower than in the North-West, -28.99% compared to the Central regions, -26.74% compared to the North and -31.21 % compared to the North-East.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange

for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Nord	61,8	63,5	64,8	66	66,2	66,2
Nord-ovest	57,8	59,9	61,4	62,7	63	63,1

Nord-est	67,3	68,5	69,4	70,5	70,7	70,5
Centro	63,2	64,1	65,6	67,2	68,1	68,3
Mezzogiorno	43	44,5	45,6	47,8	48,9	50
Sud	41	42,6	44,1	46,1	47,2	48,5
Isole	47,1	48,6	48,9	51,4	52,4	53,2
Italia	55,6	57,1	58,4	60,1	60,7	61,2

Regione	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Piemonte</i>	64,7	66,3	68	69,3	69,5	70,4	5,70	8,81
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	105,2	108	109,3	112	112,5	115	9,80	9,32
<i>Liguria</i>	66,8	68,6	70,5	72,6	72,9	73,2	6,40	9,58
<i>Lombardia</i>	52,7	55,2	56,6	57,7	58	57,9	5,20	9,87
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	107,1	108,5	111,2	112,6	113,8	114,8	7,70	7,19
<i>Veneto</i>	60,7	61,9	62,7	63,6	63,7	63,2	2,50	4,12
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	83,8	86,4	88,5	90,9	90,8	91,2	7,40	8,83
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	60,5	61,2	61,5	62,5	62,5	62,1	1,60	2,64
<i>Toscana</i>	70,9	72,2	74,1	75	76,2	75,8	4,90	6,91
<i>Umbria</i>	76,2	76,4	78,2	81,1	81,8	83,2	7,00	9,19
<i>Marche</i>	74,2	74,5	74,9	75,9	76,3	76,4	2,20	2,96
<i>Lazio</i>	53,3	54,2	55,8	57,7	58,7	59,1	5,80	10,88
<i>Abruzzo</i>	59	59,6	61,4	63,1	64,1	63,5	4,50	7,63
<i>Molise</i>	57,2	62,5	67	64,6	68,3	69,1	11,90	20,80
<i>Campania</i>	33,1	33,8	36,4	37,1	37,5	39,6	6,50	19,64
<i>Puglia</i>	41,3	43	42,7	46,3	47,8	48,9	7,60	18,40
<i>Basilicata</i>	58,2	63,8	65	67,9	67,8	68,6	10,40	17,87
<i>Calabria</i>	44	46,8	48,6	52,2	54,3	54,8	10,80	24,55
<i>Sicilia</i>	41,1	42,7	44,1	45,5	46,3	47	5,90	14,36
<i>Sardegna</i>	65,4	66,8	63,3	69,3	70,8	72	6,60	10,09

Rank	Regione	2015	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Calabria</i>	44	54,8	10,8	24,55
2	<i>Molise</i>	57,2	69,1	11,9	20,8
3	<i>Campania</i>	33,1	39,6	6,5	19,64
4	<i>Puglia</i>	41,3	48,9	7,6	18,4
5	<i>Basilicata</i>	58,2	68,6	10,4	17,87
6	<i>Sicilia</i>	41,1	47	5,9	14,36
7	<i>Lazio</i>	53,3	59,1	5,8	10,88
8	<i>Sardegna</i>	65,4	72	6,6	10,09
9	<i>Lombardia</i>	52,7	57,9	5,2	9,87
10	<i>Liguria</i>	66,8	73,2	6,4	9,58
11	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	105	115	9,8	9,32
12	<i>Umbria</i>	76,2	83,2	7	9,19

13	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	83,8	91,2	7,4	8,83
14	<i>Piemonte</i>	64,7	70,4	5,7	8,81
15	<i>Abruzzo</i>	59	63,5	4,5	7,63
16	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	107	114,8	7,7	7,19
17	<i>Toscana</i>	70,9	75,8	4,9	6,91
18	<i>Veneto</i>	60,7	63,2	2,5	4,12
19	<i>Marche</i>	74,2	76,4	2,2	2,96
20	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	60,5	62,1	1,6	2,64

Rank	Regione	2020
1	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	115,00
2	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	114,80
3	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	91,20
4	<i>Umbria</i>	83,20
5	<i>Marche</i>	76,40
6	<i>Toscana</i>	75,80
7	<i>Liguria</i>	73,20
8	<i>Sardegna</i>	72,00
9	<i>Piemonte</i>	70,40
10	<i>Molise</i>	69,10
11	<i>Basilicata</i>	68,60
12	<i>Abruzzo</i>	63,50
13	<i>Veneto</i>	63,20
14	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	62,10
15	<i>Lazio</i>	59,10
16	<i>Lombardia</i>	57,90
17	<i>Calabria</i>	54,80
18	<i>Puglia</i>	48,90
19	<i>Sicilia</i>	47,00
20	<i>Campania</i>	39,60